

APPRAISING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN BURNOUT AND JOB SATISFACTIONS AMONG PRIVATE SCHOOL TEACHERS FOR QUALITY EDUCATION IN WAMAKKO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, SOKOTO STATE

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Abstract

The study investigated on the relationship between burnout and job satisfactions among private school teachers in Wamakko local government area. It was a cross sectional survey design which consists of 92 respondents (teachers) randomly selected from three purposively selected private schools representing thirty three (33) private schools in the study area. Adopted Maslach Burnout Inventory - Educators Survey (MBI - ES) and Job Satisfactions Survey (JSS) instruments were used for collecting data from the respondents. Two research questions and one hypothesis were formulated which guided the study and the data collected were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlations with the help of SPSS Version 20. The results obtained shown the occurrences of burnout among the private school teachers for the first finding. The second finding revealed that there is significant relationship between burnout and job satisfactions of private school teachers in Wamakko local government area. The study recommended that school administrators should collaborate with their respective proprietors to find ways on how to avoid burnout among private schools' teachers so that job satisfactions can be improved for better result.

Keywords: Burnout, Job Satisfaction, Quality Education

Introduction

The term “burnout” was first used by Freudenberger (1975) to explain the phenomena of physical, emotional, and mental exhaustion. Burnout is a condition when individual is emotionally, mentally, and physically exhausted as a result of excessive and prolonged stress. It takes place when individual feel emotionally drained, and unable to meet constant demands. If the stress persists, he begins to lose the interest or motivation that could lead to work dissatisfaction. When someone feels overworked he is at risk of burnout and the induced causes may include; lack of recognition or reward for good work, unclear or overly demanding job expectations, working in a chaotic or high-pressure environment, working too much, without enough time for socializing or relaxing, lack of close, supportive relationships, taking on too many responsibilities, without enough help from others resulting in insomnia.

Private school teachers in Wamakko local government area are not stable, they move from one school to another in search of greener pasture. The fortunate ones will end up finding their ways into public schools. It is observed that teachers' brain drained from private schools to government or public schools but hardly for teachers in public schools to ever make an attempt of moving to private owned schools. Is job burnout responsible for such phenomena or lack of job satisfaction?

Burnout is a feeling of stress and frustration that an individual can experience which could culminate in attrition (Martinetz, 2012). Teacher burnout by itself is nothing new; what is new is the increasing rate at which teachers experience burnout. It typically accompanied by negative and cynical attitudes towards both colleagues and work in general (Gruenert & Whitaker, 2015). Fruedengerger (1975) was the first to publish research on the concept of burnout. He identified one sign of burnout as a feeling of exhaustion and fatigue. Fruedengerger described people who experience burnout as overachievers who put pressure on themselves, find fault with everyone, complain about everything, stay late at work, and take work home. However, they never seem to get caught up, which adds to their level of stress. In some cases, the stress becomes so overwhelming that it culminates in attrition (Clandinin, 2014).

Initially burnout was solely identified, defined, and studied clinically in the field of health care. Parker, Martin, Colmar, and Liem., (2012) argued that the three core aspects of burnout include emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and feelings of low accomplishment stemmed from a loss of idealism and enthusiasm for work (Skaalvik, 2011). There are some jobs where stress is common, due to the nature of the position, such as nursing. Over a prolonged period of time, the stress begins to accumulate, resulting in job burnout (Reeivee, 2012). In addition to medicine, fields with high-stress occupations include law, aviation, and education (Leiter, Bakker, and Maslach 2014). The attitude of some teachers toward their profession signifies dissatisfaction. The rate at which teachers are moving in and out of the profession rated it as second hand job in Nigeria. Some regarded it as punishment ground while others viewed it as last option job.

Teachers who are emotionally and physically fatigued may say they are exhausted or drained (Goldhaber & Cowan, 2014). Some teachers expressed the feelings that their work has very little impact on their students. They often complain of not wanting to get up in the morning and go to work (Martinetz, 2012). One of the most overwhelming problems for teachers is their failure to manage the environments in their classrooms (Reeves, 2012). Student misbehavior is a specific working condition strongly associated with job stress and burnout (Ratcliff, Jones, Costner, Savage-Davis, & Hunt, 2010). The research investigated on the relationship between burnout and job satisfactions among teachers of private schools in Wamakko local government area.

Theoretical Framework

The Person-Environment Fit Theory (French & Caplan, 1972) is widely accepted for studying the phenomenon of job satisfaction, stress, and burnout. In the Person-Environment Fit Theory, it is advocated that the degree to which individuals are compatible to, or fit to their environment is related to the degree to which they are stressed. According to Edwards, Caplan, and Harrison (1998), there are several distinctions relative to fit. The first distinction is between the individual and the environment, the second is between the objective representation and the subjective representation, the third is between demands and abilities (Edwards et al.). "Misfit between demands and abilities induces coping and defense mechanisms, which in turn influence objective and subjective environments" (Brewer & McMahan-Landers, 2003, p. 37).

According to Brewer and McMahan-Landers (p. 126), "Stress can occur if there is a mismatch between the reality of the work environment (objective) and an individual's

perceptions of the work environment (subjective).” He noted that teachers who experience stress over long periods of time may experience what is known as burnout.

Locke, (1976) defined job satisfaction as an emotion of being happy or comfortable with one’s job. According Aziri (2011) job satisfaction is a feeling of success and achievement of workers in areas where they are operating. This feeling is geared more towards enhancing successful productivity in school. Job satisfaction is also indirectly related to performing a task with a happy, successful and adequate remuneration given to the efforts that have been made.

Burnout is often associated with satisfaction in the workplace. To avoid burnout, job satisfaction in individuals should be met. In the education sector, job satisfaction becomes important because the quality of education depends on the quality and efficiency of the teacher. In addition, the findings from Apandi (2003) showed that job satisfaction has a negative correlation with emotional exhaustion but correlated with the length of time a person is having a career.

However, the theory emphasizes that job satisfaction largely depends on individual’s matching of those distinctions and inappropriate matching resulting to dissatisfaction or otherwise called job burnout. The higher the level of fitness the easier the job and the lesser the amount of stress experienced by the teacher, indeed the higher the level of job satisfaction. Other likely causes of job burnout include; lack of job collaborations, when feel isolated and teachers` inability to handle his/her classroom. Work environment and the lack of collaboration with colleagues can contribute to the feeling of burnout (Dierking & Fox, 2012). When teachers perceive that their relationships with colleagues are dysfunctional, they feel isolated (Cooper & Conley, 2013). When they feel isolated, their stress levels begin to increase and the accumulation of stress ultimately leads to job burnout (Levine & Marcus, 2010).

Base on the above theoretical explanation, the researcher was stimulated to ascertain the existence of burnout and job satisfactions among teachers in private schools and examine the relationship between job burnout and job satisfactions among teachers of private schools in Wamakko Local Government Area.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to;

Identify the existence of job burnout amongst private school teachers in Wamakko local government area.

Identify whether private school teachers in Wamakko local government area are satisfied with their job.

Examine the relationship between burnout and job satisfaction amongst private school teachers in wamakko local government area.

Research Question and Hypothesis

Is there job burnout amongst private school teachers in wamakko local government area?
Are private school teachers in Wamakko Local Government Area satisfied with their job?

There is no significant relationship between burnout and job satisfaction among private school teachers in Wamakko Local Government Area, Sokoto State.

Methodology

The study used correlational survey design and three schools were selected purposively to represent thirty three (33) approved private schools in Wamakko local government area (NAPPS, 2021). The sample size consists of 92 respondents (teachers) randomly selected from 126 staff of three selected schools with help of Research Average, (2006). The schools were Alheri School Guiwa low cost, Success School Western Bypass and Khalil Fodiyo School Arkilla all geographically located in Wamakko local government area.

Instrumentation

Two questionnaires were used for data collection. The first that measured teacher burnout is Maslach Burnout Inventory - Educators Survey (MBI - ES) and the second questionnaires that measured teacher job satisfaction is Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS). The content validity was obtained after the validation of items of the questionnaire by experts in guidance and counselling and educational psychology. The pilot study findings carry out in Unity comprehensive school (private school) in Sokoto North local government area, shows that both instrument of burnout and job satisfaction had high reliability with Cronbach alpha values of .82 and .87 respectively.

Results

Is there job burnout amongst Private School Teachers in Wamakko local government area.

Table 1: Teachers Job Burnout

S/N	Item	Disgree F (%)	Agree F (%)
1	I feel emotionally drained from my work	33 (35.9)	59 (64.1)
2	I feel fatigued when I get up in the morning and have face another day on the job	23(25)	69(75)
3	I feel very energetic	36(39.1)	59(60.9)
4	I feel frustrated by my job	71(77.2)	21(22.8)
5	I feel exhilarated after working closely with my students	33(35.9)	59(64.1)
6	I feel like I'm at the end of my rope	65(77.7)	27(39.3)
7	I feel I am positively influencing other people's lives through my work	18(19.6)	74(80.4)
8	I feel I treat some students as if they were impersonal objects	66(71.7)	26(28.3)
9	I feel used up at the end of the work day	47(51.1)	45(48.9)
10	I worry that this job is hardening me emotionally	47(51.1)	45(48.9)

The table 1 shows the existence burnout among teachers of private schools in the study area. Where I feel emotionally drained from my work account for 64%, I feel fatigued when I get up in the morning and have face another day on the job 75%, I feel used up at

the end of the work day 48%, I feel frustrated by my job 22.8% and I worry that this job is hardening me emotionally 48.9%. these results confirmed the existence of burnout among teachers of private schools in Wamakko local government area.

Are Private School Teachers in Wamakko local government area satisfied with their job?

Table 2: Teachers job satisfactions

S/N	Item	Agree F (%)	Disagree F (%)
1	Teaching provides me with an opportunity to advance professionally	92(100)	00(00)
2	Teacher income is adequate for normal expenses	47(51.1)	45(48.9)
3	Teaching provides an opportunity to use a variety of skills	86(93.5)	6(6.5)
4	Insufficient income keeps me from living the way I want to live	63(68.5)	29(31.5)
5	Teaching provides for a secure future	71(77.2)	21(22.8)
6	If I could earn what I earn now, I would take any job	47(51.1)	45(48.9)
7	Teaching provides me the opportunity to help my students learn	77(83.7)	15(16.3)
8	I like the people with whom I work	74(80.4)	18(19.6)
9	I never feel secured in my teaching job	42(45.7)	50(54.3)
10	Teaching provides me limited opportunities for advancement	56(70.7)	27(29.3)

The table 2 indicates the existence job satisfactions among teachers of private schools in the study area. Where; Teaching provides me with an opportunity to advance professionally 100%, Teacher income is adequate for normal expenses 51.1%, Teaching provides an opportunity to use a variety of skills 93%, Teaching provides for a secure future 77.2%, I like the people with whom I work 80.4% and Teaching provides me the opportunity to help my students learn 83.7%. The result obtained confirmed that job satisfactions also exist among private school teachers in Wamakko local government area. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected otherwise the alternative hypothesis is accepted. H_0 : There is no relationship between burnout and job satisfactions amongst private school teachers in Wamakko Local Government Area.

Table 3: Relationship between burnout and job satisfactions among private secondary school teachers in wamakko local government area.

		Burnout	Job Satisfaction
Burnout	Pearson Correlation	1	.305**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.003
	N	92	92
Job Satisfactions	Pearson Correlation	.305**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	
	N	92	92

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results from Table 3 shows that there is a significant relationship between burnout and job satisfaction ($r=.305, p<.05$). With this result the null hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion

From the analysis of the data generated in this study, it is confirmed that burnout is not only associated with health related job like nursing rather it is also takes place in teaching job among teachers in privately established schools. The finding concord with Leiter et al. (2014) In addition to medicine, fields with high-stress occupations include law, aviation, and education.

Levine and Marcus, (2010) and Cooper and Conley, (2013), further lamented that, when teachers perceive that their relationships with colleagues are dysfunctional, they feel isolated. When they feel isolated, their stress levels begin to increase and the accumulation of stress ultimately leads to job burnout.

The analysis also confirmed that there is significant relationship between burnout and job satisfactions among teachers working in private schools. It is in line with The Person-Environment Fit Theory (French & Caplan, 1972) which is widely accepted for studying the phenomenon of job satisfaction, stress, and burnout. The theory emphasizes that job satisfaction is largely depend on individual matching of those distinctions and inappropriate matching result to dissatisfaction or otherwise called job burnout. The higher the level of fitness the easier the job and the lesser the amount of stress experienced by the teacher and indeed the higher the level of job satisfaction. It also concord with Apandi (2003) who opined that job satisfaction has a negative correlation with emotional exhaustion but correlated with the length of time a person is having a career.

Conclusion

The study confirmed the occurrence of burnout syndrome among private schools teachers, and it is the contributing factor responsible for having unstable teachers in private schools in Wamakko local government area. Burnout and teachers job satisfactions are related, promoting one result in the lowering another.

Recommendations

1. Teachers should be aware of the problems associated with burnout and how these problems may adversely affect their professional and personal lives. Annual teacher's conferences, seminars and workshops could be used to sensitize the members on how to avoid and overcome burnout at working places.
2. Since there is relationship between burnout and job satisfactions, the public, privates and NGOs should diversify their efforts toward improving teachers job satisfactions, so that burnout in teaching profession can be minimizes to the barest level.
3. There is also need for more research to examine the relationship on the categories of staff in relation to their respective years of experiences.

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